

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SPOCK3

(SPARC (osteonectin), cwcv and kazal like domains proteoglycan 3)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	50859/Q9BQ16
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being

evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.27 out of 5 (rank #3315, 86.7th percentile). The individual score components include 1.33 of 3 for genetics, and 1.94 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SPOCK3, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SPOCK3 is annotated to GO terms from the Structural Stabilization and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of SPOCK3 is confidently detected in oligodendrocytes, oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC), endothelial cells, and both excitatory and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

SPOCK3 function and association with AD is described below and was identified within TREAT-AD as participating within a core module associated with AD pathology and dementia(1). To facilitate the efforts of the scientific community to expand our understanding of the role of SPOCK3 in AD, we have developed a basic target enablement package (TEP) consisting of characterized antibody for both biochemical and histological purposes, purified protein, and a full bioinformatics characterization of SPOCK3. We hope that the availability of core validated reagents will promote future investigations into the role of SPOCK3 in AD pathogenesis.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

SPOCK3/Testicular-3 is a 436 amino acid member of the SPOCK-family of secreted extracellular matrix proteoglycans(2, 3) that is highly expressed in brain(4). SPOCK3 contains three functional domains: a Kazal-like inhibitory domain that is involved in binding to metalloproteinases capturing them in an enzyme-substrate complex; an EF hand domain that is involved in binding calcium in the extracellular region, and a thyroglobulin domain that cooperates with the Kazal-like domain in metalloproteinase inhibition(4, 5). SPOCK family members, including SPOCK3, modulate oncogenic invasion within different cancer models(6-8), likely by inhibiting matrix metalloproteinases from repelling encroaching tumour cell adhesion(8, 9). In brain, SPOCK3 is implicated in CNS development and axon pathfinding, as the SPOCK3 knockout mouse demonstrates corpus callosum structural abnormalities and decreases in anxiety and social engagement(10). In humans, variants of SPOCK3 are implicated in elevated risk for ADHD(11), another link with neurodevelopment and synaptic function.

SPOCK3 was identified in a multiomic biomarkers study as potentially associated with brain aging(12), suggesting a possible role for SPOCK3 in age-related neurological events. A recent examination of the Ashkenazi Jewish population in GWAS studies identified a link between SPOCK3 and Alzheimer's disease(13), based upon an intergenic variant risk association, implying a possible connection between SPOCK3 gene regulation and AD risk. Intriguingly, a recent clinical pathological study looking for mediated linkage between the APOE4 allele and amyloid load and tau tangle intensity found that SPOCK3 (testicular-3) was one of the two main proteins mediating the association between APOE4 and tau tangles in post-mortem AD brains(14). This is consistent with the data contributing to the current project, in which SPOCK3 was identified as a member of a proteomic module associated with both pathological progression and cognitive decline in AD(1). While the mechanism remains to be elucidated, the connection between SPOCK3 and AD warrants further investigation, and supports a growing body of evidence suggesting a potential role of matrix metalloproteinase inhibition in susceptibility for AD pathogenesis.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of SPOCK3 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

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